

EVALUATION OF ANTI-ANXIETY ACTIVITY: ASSESSING THE EFFICACY OF ETHANOLIC GINGER EXTRACT ON ALBINO WISTAR RATS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Anxiety disorders are among the most prevalent mental health conditions worldwide, affecting individuals of all ages. The search for effective and safe treatment options for anxiety has led to the exploration of natural products, including medicinal plants. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) has been traditionally used for its various medicinal properties, including its anxiolytic effects. **Aim & objective:** This study aims to evaluate the anti-anxiety activity of ethanolic ginger extract in albino Wistar rats. **Material and methods:** Albino Wistar rats were randomly divided into different groups: control, standard (Diazepam), and test (receiving different doses of 200mg/kg, 300mg/kg, 400mg/kg of ethanolic ginger extract). The animals were subjected to established behavioural models to assess anxiety-like behaviour, such as the elevated plus maze. The ethanolic ginger extract was administered orally, and the effects were compared with the control and standard groups. **Results:** The results of the study showed that the ethanolic ginger extract exhibited significant anti-anxiety activity in the albino Wistar rats. The extract-treated groups displayed reduced anxiety-like behaviour compared to the control group, as evidenced by increased time spent in the open arms of the elevated plus maze and demonstrated significance at ($P < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** The results suggest that ginger may hold promise as a natural alternative for the management of anxiety disorders via multiple mechanism.

Keywords: *Anxiety, Anti-anxiety, elevated plus maze, Ginger, Diazepam.*

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety disorders are a prevalent psychiatric condition affecting millions of individuals worldwide, leading to significant impairments in daily functioning and quality of life. Anxiety is a common mental health condition experienced by individuals in response to various stress or perceived threats, characterized by feelings of fear, apprehension, worry, and nervousness. It is a mental health condition that can significantly impact an individual's daily life and overall well-being.^[1] Anxiety can vary in intensity and duration. While the excessive or persistent anxiety that interferes with daily functioning and quality of life may indicate an anxiety disorder. Several neurotransmitters and neuromodulators play important roles in the regulation of anxiety. These substances act within the brain and nervous system to modulate mood, emotions, and stress responses.^[2] Some of the key modulators implicated in anxiety include Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid (GABA), GABA is the primary inhibitory neurotransmitter in the brain and plays a crucial role in reducing neuronal excitability. Low levels of GABA activity or impaired GABAergic neurotransmission have been associated with anxiety disorders. Drugs that enhance GABA activity are commonly used to treat anxiety. Serotonin (5-HT), Serotonin is a neurotransmitter involved in mood regulation, emotions, and stress responses. Dysregulation of the serotonergic system has been implicated in various anxiety disorders, including generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) and obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD).^[3] Medications that increase serotonin levels are used to treat anxiety. Also, other neurotransmitters play important role in anxiety disorder such as Norepinephrine, Dopamine.

The pharmacological management of anxiety often involves the use of anti-anxiety drugs, such as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), benzodiazepines but their long-term efficacy and potential adverse effects have raised concerns. As a result, researchers have been exploring alternative treatments with fewer side effects and greater effectiveness.^[4]

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), a commonly used culinary and medicinal herb, has gained attention for its potential therapeutic properties, including its anxiolytic effects. The active components of ginger, such as gingerols and shogaols, have demonstrated various pharmacological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and neuroprotective properties. However, limited research has been conducted to evaluate the anti-anxiety potential of ginger extract, particularly on animal models.^[5,6]

In this article, we aim to investigate the anti-anxiety activity of ginger extract using an animal model, specifically Albino Wistar rats. Animal models play a crucial role in studying anxiety disorders and assessing the efficacy of potential therapeutic interventions. Albino Wistar rats have been widely employed in preclinical research due to their physiological and genetic similarities to humans.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ginger material

The dried ginger rhizome of *Zingiber officinale* brought from the local supermarket Hyderabad, Telangana. This dried ginger has been used as a spice and medicinal purpose from the ancient times.^[7] Dried ginger was powdered using motor and pestle and extracted using Soxhlet apparatus.

Drugs

Diazepam (Valium 5 Tablet) was obtained from the Apollo pharmacy in Hyderabad, it is administrated at dose of 2mg/kg orally.

Preparation of ginger extract

The dried rhizome of ginger is collected and are powdered by the use mortar and pestle. The powdered materials [50gm] were extracted with 95% ethanol by using Soxhlet apparatus for 12 hours at a temperature not exceeding the boiling point. Then the extract was concentrated using heating mantle at the temperature not exceeding 60⁰c. Then the crude extract is collected, weighed, and stored in room temperature for future use.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

- **Alkaloids:** A few drops of Dragendorff reagent were added ginger extract along the sides of test tube. The formation of orange – red precipitate confirms the present of Alkaloids.
- **Glycosides:** 1ml of distilled water and 0.5ml of NaOH are added to crude extract the formation of yellow color shows the presence of glycosides.^[8]
- **Flavonoids:** Alkaline reagent test- Extract was mixed with water in a test tube and shaken. Few drops of sodium hydroxide were added, formation of intense yellow color which becomes colorless on further addition of dilute Hydrochloric acid indicate the presence of flavonoids.
- **Saponins:** Extract was mixed with water in a test tube and heat. Few drops of olive oil were added and shaken. Formation of soluble emulsion indicated the presence of Saponins.
- **Tannins:** Extract was mixed with water in a test tube and heated. The mixture was filtered and 0.1% of ferric chloride was added. Appearance of brownish green coloration indicates the presence of tannins.
- **Steroid:** Extract was dissolved in 2ml of Chloroform and few drops of Sulphuric acid was added to form a lower layer. A reddish-brown color at the interface indicates the presence of steroid.
- **Anthraquinones:** Extract was collected in a dry test tube and 5mls of chloroform was added and shaken for 5minutes it was then filtered and the filtrate was shaken with an equal volume of 100% ammonia solution. A pink violet or red color in ammonia lower layer indicates the presence of free Anthraquinones.^[9]
- **Phenols:** The extract was dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water and 2 ml of 1% solution of Gelatin containing 10% NaCl was added to it. White precipitate indicates the presence of phenol compounds.
- **Oxalates:** 5ml of the extract was treated with 1ml of concentrated sulphuric acid, this was allowed to stand for an hour and two drops of potassium permanganate was added, the formation of steady red color indicate the presence of oxalate.^[10]

Experimental Animals

Albino Wistar rats (200-250 g) of either sex were purchased from Vyas labs and the animals were maintained in a well-ventilated room with 12:12 hour light/dark cycle in polypropylene cages. Standard pellet fed and water ad libitum was provided throughout experimentation period. Rats are acclimatized to the new environment for one week before treatment. The animals are divided into 5 groups each containing (n=6).

Experimental design

Thirty animals (n=6) are used in the study in each group it consists of 6 animals (n=6). Drugs is orally administrated using gavage needle before 2 hours of testing. Animals are trained on EPG prior one week before administrating the drug.

- **Group I:** Control
- **Group II:** Diazepam (2mg/kg) administered orally as standard.
- **Group III:** Ginger extract (200mg/kg) administered orally.
- **Group IV:** Ginger extract (300mg/kg) administered orally.
- **Group V:** Ginger extract (400mg/kg) administered orally.

After 2 hours administration of drug the animals are following test for screening of anxiolytic activity.

ELEVATED PLUS MAZE (EPM)

The elevated plus-maze, developed by Pellow and File (1986) and modified by Kulkarni (1991), is a novel test selective identification of anxiogenic and anxiolytic drugs effects in rodents. The plus maze apparatus consists of two open arm (16*5cm for mice and 50* 10cm for rats) and two closed arms (16*5*12 cm for mice and 50*10*40 cm for rats) with an open roof with entire maze elevated (25 cm for mice and 50 cm for rats).^[11] The animals are placed individually at the centre of the plus maze with their head facing an open arm. During the 5-min test, the preference of the animal for the first entry, the number of entries into open or closed arms and the time spent in each arm of the maze are recorded.^[12]

Statistical analysis

Results are expressed in mean \pm SEM and analysis is done using one way ANOVA test with *P value* <0.001 was considered significant and statistical comparison among the group is done using GraphPad Prism software version 8.

Table 2: Effects of ethanolic ginger extract on anxiety activity using elevated plus**RESULTS****Preliminary Phytochemical Screening**

Preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis of Ginger ethanolic extract in Table 1 revealed the presence of Alkaloid and flavonoid, Phenol, Steroid, anthraquinone, tannin, and saponin were present in ginger extract. Glycosides is absent in ginger extract.

Table 1: Results of phytochemical of screening ethanolic ginger extract

S. No	Phytochemicals	Ginger extract
1.	Alkaloid	Present
2.	Flavonoid	Present
3.	Tannins	Present
4.	Saponins	Present
5.	Glycosides	Absent
6.	Steroid	Present
7.	Anthraquinone	Present
8.	Phenolics	Present
9.	Oxalate	Present

Elevated plus maze (EPM)

Ethanolic Ginger extract on administrating orally in three different doses (200mg/kg, 300mg/kg, 400mg/kg) shows significant increase in anxiolytic activity with increase in dose. There is a significant difference in the time spent in open arm in three different doses. When ginger extract (group III, IV, V) in comparison with Diazepam (group II) show highly significant $P < 0.001$ with increase in time spent in open arm in EPM test when compared with control (group I).

These observations result [Table 1] shows that ethanolic ginger extract have anti- anxiety activity.

maze test			
Group	Treatment	Time spent in open arms in sec (Mean±SEM)	Time spent in closed arms in sec (Mean±SEM)
I	Control	11.1±1.09	288±1.09
II	Diazepam (2mg/kg)	157±2.43 ^a	149±2.43
III	Ginger extract (200mg/kg)	42.5±1.39 ^{a, b}	261±1.39 ^c
IV	Ginger extract (300mg/kg)	79.4±3.49 ^{a, b}	229.5±3.49 ^c
V	Ginger extract (400mg/kg)	96.6±1.9 ^{a, b}	204.6±1.9 ^c

One way ANOVA test with P value <0.001 was considered significant and statistical comparison among the group is done using GraphPad Prism software version 8. n=6

^a $P < 0.001$ Highly significant (comparing group II, III, IV, V with group I)

^b $P < 0.001$ Highly significant (comparing group III, IV, V with group II in open arms)

^c $P < 0.001$ Highly significant (comparing group III, IV, V with group II in closed arms)

Figure 1: Effects of ethanolic ginger extract on anxiety activity using elevated plus maze test
^a $P < 0.001$ Highly significant (comparing group II, III, IV, V with group I). ^b $P < 0.001$ Highly significant (comparing group III, IV, V with group II in open arms). ^c $P < 0.001$ Highly significant (comparing group III, IV, V with group II in closed arms). GE- ginger extract.

DISCUSSION

Several neurotransmitters and neuromodulators play important roles in the regulation of anxiety. These substances act within the brain and nervous system to modulate mood, emotions, and stress responses. GABA is the primary inhibitory neurotransmitter in the brain and plays a crucial role in reducing neuronal excitability. Low levels of GABA activity or impaired GABAergic neurotransmission have been associated with anxiety disorders. Drugs that enhance GABA activity are commonly used to treat anxiety. Serotonin (5-HT), Serotonin is a neurotransmitter involved in mood regulation, emotions, and stress responses. Dysregulation of the serotonergic system has been implicated in various anxiety disorders, including generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) and obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). Medications that increase serotonin levels are used to treat anxiety. Norepinephrine is a neurotransmitter and stress hormone involved in the body's "fight or flight" response. Dysregulation of the noradrenergic system has been implicated in conditions such as panic disorder and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Medications that block the action of norepinephrine, such as beta-blockers, are sometimes used to reduce symptoms of anxiety.^[13]

Medications like serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), benzodiazepines and other anti-anxiety drugs having potential adverse effect due to this reason many researchers exploring for alternative with less side effects. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is an alternative which shows significant anti-anxiety activity with less side effect. The ginger consists of major components of gingerol, shogaols, and phenolic compounds and flavonoids which shows anxiolytic activity.^[14] Further studies are required to know anxiolytic property of ginger.

In the current study, the 400 mg/kg dose of ginger significantly increased the number of entries in open arm and duration of time spent in open arm in EPM model when compared to 200mg/kg and 300mg/kg. when comparing with diazepam the ginger extract showing significantly less anxiolytic activity but ginger having less toxicity effects when compared with diazepam.

CONCLUSION

The present work demonstrated that the ethanolic extract of ginger had anxiolytic activity in albino rats in animal models of anxiety like EPM test models. The 400 mg/kg dose of ginger significantly increased the number of entries in open arm and duration of time spent in open arm in EPM model when compared to 200mg/kg and 300mg/kg. The anti-anxiety effects of ginger have been demonstrated in both animal with evidence suggesting that ginger may have comparable efficacy to conventional anti-anxiety medications. While more research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms underlying ginger's anti-anxiety effects, the available evidence suggests that it may act by modulating the levels of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and GABA in the brain.

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